

EMPLOYMENT OF FREE-FALL BOMBS ON MULTIPLE TARGETS IN A SECTION FLIGHT

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ABSTRACT

This article analyses the best tactic to employ four free-fall bombs by two aircrafts in two different targets. Two tactics were evaluated: each aircraft employing two free-fall bombs simultaneously, each aircraft attacking one target; and both aircrafts employing a single free-fall bomb in each target. Based on calculations, the best tactic is that each aircraft releases its weaponry on its own target. Employments with multiple bombs increase the designation area and increases the probability of a single impact more than two aircrafts attacking the same target. Once the results are theoretical, an empirical evaluation is still necessary.

Keywords: Air interdiction, Suppression of Enemy Air Defence, Close Air Support, Air Force.

INTRODUCTION

During the war, attack aircrafts can be allocated to execute air interdiction missions. These missions usually require the interdiction or destruction of ground targets using free-fall bombs. Free-fall bombs are conventional aircraft-delivered bombs that follow a ballistic trajectory without the aid of a guidance system. To evaluate how the resources will be allocated, each air interdiction mission has its probability of success evaluated. One of its factors is the probability of a single bomb impact on the designated target. Sometimes, more than one target is designated for a mission, and the flight leader must decide how best will he use his

assets. In this article, the following scenario will be analysed: a section flight of two aircrafts carrying four free-fall bombs to attack two different targets. The leader can choose either to have each aircraft attack a different target, or have both aircrafts attacking both targets, releasing half their weaponry on each one. The targets' dimensions are 10x10x4m and the circular error probable (CEP) is 13m.

PROBABILITY OF SUCCESS FOR EACH AIRCRAFT ATTACKING A DIFFERENT TARGET

Considering a ripple of 15m between the impact of two bombs, the designation area of the attack is 250m², illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1 - Attack with two free-fall bombs

Source: (2019) Knapp Attack

The red circle represents the blast radius; the yellow circle represents the CEP; the green rectangle represents the designation area. And the white square represents the target.

For this designation area and the informed CEP, according to the employment evaluation software Knapp Attack, the probability of a single impact is 39%. Considering there are two different targets, both targets must be attacked so the mission is successful. So, multiplying the probability of success of attacking each target, the total probability of success is 15%.

PROBABILITY OF SUCCESS FOR BOTH AIRCRAFTS ATTACKING A BOTH TARGETS

Releasing a single free-fall bomb, the designation area reduces for 100m². illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 2 - Attack with one free-fall bomb

Source: (2019) Knapp Attack

For this designation area and the informed CEP, the probability of a single impact is 18%. Because there are two aircrafts attacking, the probability of success for a single target is 32%, by multiplying the probability that both aircrafts miss the target. Considering there are two different targets and multiplying the probability of success of attacking each target, the total probability of success is 11%.

CONCLUSION

Comparing both analysed tactics, the conclusion is that it is better that each aircraft attack a separate target with all their weaponry available. It was proven it is more advantageous to have a larger

designation area than having two aircrafts attacking a smaller designation area.

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